

School and Community Relationship Management: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: School-based management (SBM) is a management model that provides flexibility and freedom to schools that are expected to be able to manage and develop education with good education management in accordance with the potential, demands and needs that exist in schools. The management of SBM that occurs in school and community relations will provide a process of fostering and developing the personal growth of students so that it has an impact on improving the quality of schools. The problem is quite complex, one of which is the relationship between the school and the community.

KEYWORDS: School Based Management, School and Community Relations, Education Quality

INTRODUCTION

To achieve the success of goals in the field of education, many factors influence, one of which is the relationship between the school and the community that supports each other (Noviantiani & Harmonika, 2021). The relationship between the school and the community essentially has an important role in fostering and developing the personal growth of students. The school's relationship with the community aims to increase community participation, as well as support from the community, involve the community, and generate a sense of responsibility for the continuity of education programs in schools effectively and efficiently (Indraningrum, 2018). Various problems faced by schools are also part of community problems. This requires team work between the two. Therefore, community involvement is very important as a source of aspirations and a benchmark in achieving quality. Schools are institutions in which all aspirations of the community are educated for a brighter future (Haryati et al., 2021). Schools are educational institutions as a forum for transforming the balance between values and morals to students in the process of implementing effective learning, schools are required to strive to make innovations to improve the quality of education in advancing institutional quality nationally. To achieve the success of the goals and the quality of education, many factors influence, one of which is the relationship between schools and the community that supports each other, effective school-community relations can be seen in the level of community participation in school programs because the responsibility for providing education is togetherness between the government, people and society. parents, and the community Schools are institutions in which all aspirations of the community are educated for a brighter future (Haryati et al., 2021).

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LITERATURE REVIEW

According to E. Mulyasa, revealed that the most important thing in the implementation of School-Based Management is the management of the components of the school itself. The school components are (1) curriculum management and teaching programs, (2) education staff management, (3) student management, (4) financial management and management financing, (5) school

relationship management with the community, (6) management of special services, (7) management of facilities and infrastructure (Kurniawati & Pardimin, 2021). By giving freedom to schools to regulate school life in accordance with the potential, demands, and needs of the school concerned, which is adjusted to the vision and mission of the school. Based on the vision, mission, and educational goals, schools establish various programs and activities to achieve goals by utilizing the various potentials that are available and can be explored in schools and the community around the school (Seriyaniti et al., 2020). Public Relations or Public Relations according to Jefkins in (Juhji et al, 2020) is a planned and sustainable business with the aim of creating and maintaining good will. School-Based Management (SBM) is an effort to develop ideas and ideas to actualize schools in order to meet the demands of government policies, namely the implementation of decentralized education in which the government places schools as independent educational institutions. School-based management is the independent management of schools and refers to the tendency to allow more autonomy to be managed by schools in making decisions about management, namely in the use of human, material and financial resources.

The decentralization of autonomous education from the government to schools aims to empower the role of each unit in schools and the community in an effort to solve educational problems in the field. In fact, there are not a few educational problems that must be shared responsibly and can be solved by schools and the community without involving the central government. The strategy for implementing SBM in schools is expected to be an alternative in order to improve the quality of education in schools that emphasizes the curriculum for implementing learning, student affairs, education personnel, infrastructure development, finance (financing), culture, and school and community relations. SBM is expected to have a great opportunity to boost the quality of decentralized education in the era of regional autonomy. The implementation of SBM relies on quality human resources, this shows that the ability of school principals, staff and education personnel plays an important role in developing new ideas for improving the quality of education in schools through the functions and objectives of SBM. The effectiveness of implementing SBM in schools is expected to be an alternative in order to improve the quality of education through school independence and creativity. The success of SBM can be measured through indicators that have been determined by education stakeholders, which refer to improving the quality of education in schools and communities that are able to go beyond the central education bureaucracy.¹⁴ SBM is felt to have the potential to improve management at the school level, the role of the community, management efficiency and educational equity. Decentralized education places schools as independent schools, institutions that can set policies, and regulate and improve networks which are expected to improve the quality of management performance (cooperation can be done with anyone and any party) as an effort to improve education.

METHOD

Destination

This study aims to determine the process of school management with the community in schools, whether the management of school management with the community is in accordance with the established policies, so the question in this integrative study is "How? management of school management with the community? "

Design

The methodology in this study uses the PRISMA method. The search process involves extracting relevant literature using a transparent search methodology.

Search Method

The online database that is relevant to this integrative study is about the management of school and community relations using a search engine in the form of Google Scholar with the keywords "school and community relations management". The search for relevant articles ranged from the year of publication 2015-2021 after which the articles were entered into the literature review table based on the inclusion criteria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

This section reports on the main findings drawn from several articles the author has read. The articles reviewed are research conducted in several countries in the world. The table describes the results of the literature study conducted by the author. Research has been conducted in several schools and universities.

Table 1. Results of Literature Review

No	Title Method Results	Author and year of publication	Type of Organization	Country	Method	Result
1	Implementation of School-Based Management Program in Bicol Secondary Schools	Dorren D. Arenque dan 2021	school	Filipina	deskriptif dan komparatif	School stakeholders can form strong relationships with parents and other stakeholders to involve them in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school activities that are directly related to student learning. Proven to be a group mover, collaborative initiatives should be a key feature of SBM implementation
2	School Based Management Within no The Framework of Autonomy at SMP Negeri 1 Rejang Lebong	Hamengkubuwono	school	Indonesia	Kualitatif	The results of the study indicate that it provides an effective and efficient influence and evaluates existing programs in schools. School Management and Public Relations The school accommodates the aspirations of the community through the school committee consisting of the guardians of the students.
3	Linking school based management and school effectiveness: The influence of Self based management, motivation and effectiveness in the Arab education system in Israel	Khalid Arar and Muhammed Abu Nasra	school	Arab	kualitatif	There is a positive relationship between all dimensions of self-management (decision making, resource and personnel management, resource availability, and organizational structure) and school effectiveness.

4	School-Based Management In Southeast Asia (Mbs-Sa): Demands Or Education Needs? (Educational Management Studies in Thailand and Indonesia)	Deny Setiawan	school	Indonesia		To support the improvement and acceleration of improving the quality of human resources in the field of education in accordance with field conditions to solve problems more quickly and effectively
5	School-Based Management: Alternative Strategies in Quality Competition	Busthomi Ibrohim 2018	Scholl	Indonesia	Kualitatif	With MBS, principals, teachers and students have the opportunity to innovate and improvise in schools related to curriculum, learning, managerial and other issues. SBM also demands the creation of a new institutional structure and culture, which includes: formation of school boards, development of school strategic planning, development of school annual plans, conducting internal monitoring, self-assessment, compiling annual reports, conducting school opinion surveys of school stakeholders.
6	Effectiveness of School-Based Management Practices in Increasing Community Participation and Implementing School Programs	Deitje Adolfien Scholl Katuuk, 2018		Indonesia	Kualitatif	The results show that SBM will strengthen the substantive nature of SBM as an instrument and strategy for strengthening authority, autonomy, and empowerment, and school development.

2. Discussion

Studies on school-based management (SBM) that focus on school-community relations have been carried out in various countries. The table above shows that research studies on school-based management (SBM) on schoolcommunity relations have been carried out in schools. Based on the results of a literature review and review of the sources obtained, the analysis shows that the forms of participation include involvement in programming activities, namely planning development programs, participation and funding efforts involving parents and school committees, participation in the implementation of school programs, and participation in supervision through School Committee. Second, the effectiveness of SBM in improving SBM program implementation in schools and can encourage the making of work plans to include SBM in the future, for the benefit of schools and communities. Reimers et al. (2007) support this statement by suggesting three significant explanations for why school-based management (SBM) struggles to narrow the educational equity gap. First, most high achieving schools are based in urban areas and have significant financial backing; second, SBM works well for people with adequate leadership and shared mission among school employees because of the school's organizational processes and framework; and third, school management and political processes undermine local initiatives in the most disadvantaged schools.

CONCLUSION

General it can be concluded that SBM School stakeholders can form strong relationships with parents and other stakeholders to involve them in planning, implementing, and evaluating school activities that are directly related to student learning. The relationship between the school and the community itself includes a reciprocal relationship between the school and the community and institutions. Community participation is important in the process of school relations with the community. Community information needs as one indicator of the implementation of school relationship management with the community itself. SBM is a good step to support the improvement and acceleration of improving the quality of human resources in the field of education in accordance with field conditions to solve problems more quickly and effectively Guaranteed resources to support the implementation of decentralized education from centralization are able to create a better system in the implementation of SBM related with the development and implementation of education. With the availability of supporting resources as operational implementers who are quite capable among policy makers, systems and structures will be more responsive to conditions on the ground and bring better results.

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